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ST. THOMAS AQUINAS IN FRONT OF TV OR TACTILE ANTI-THEORETICALITY OF MARSHALL MCLUHAN'S MEDIA THEORY

Abstract. This article discusses the historical sources of Marshall McLuhan's anti-theoretical media analysis and attempts to reconstruct the philosophical roots of alternative practical and creative understanding proposed by the media theorist. Relying on a variety of arguments, McLuhan spoke out against theoretical thinking that restricts understanding. Unfortunately, his statements have been structured very poorly so far. From McLuhan's point of view, distrust in theoretical perspective is related to the peculiarity of the theory to limit the possibilities of many approaches to a single one and there is a need for a meta-perspective of the approach that can encompass the totality of all possible perspectives. That meta-perspective proposed by McLuhan could be called a performance of various practices, provoking the experiences of the information user so that he/ she inevitably draws some general conclusions, based on integrating all the information he/she can get. The article pays particular attention to the origins of such a position in the history of philosophy, which, according to McLuhan's own hints, could be sought in Thomas Aquinas's theory of synaesthesia. The article also draws attention to the way this perspective is told, to the revival of some ancient genres in McLuhan's later texts and to the desire to make the reader with a book feel as if in front of TV, which for McLuhan was a technological substitute for what was touch for Thomas Aquinas - the sense that unites the information of all other senses

Keywords: history of media philosophy, practical criticism, communication of ideas, experience.

Introduction

McLuhan repeatedly tried to assure that he had no theory of communication and was generally not involved in what might be called scientific communication. McLuhan said he was not explaining, only exploring (Stearn 1967: 35). Moreover, he assured he was not using any methodology in his research and did not even have any point of view (McLuhan 1970: 4). He was just observing people's activities. Theory, as McLuhan argued, is a way of seeing, which limits understanding by pre-determined expectations and makes it possible to describe only one possibility out of many.

This ambiguity is not the author's style; it is McLuhan's purposefully developed "otherness" of media theory (Sodeika 2009: 149). Students once asked McLuhan why his articles in newspapers were so clear and simple, and the books were so complex and unclear. McLuhan replied that it depended on the difference between the perspectives of explanation and research. If you want to explain something, you must simplify your position. The consequence is that it is impossible to say anything new. And in his books, he did not seek to explain anything, he only explored and tested different possibilities of media cognition and description (McLuhan 1970: 6).

This article seeks to identify and systematize the key features of McLuhan's anti-theoretical media theory, its origins, and possible ways of influencing the reader, i.e. what McLuhan opposed in his texts by a variety of means. Although the scientific problem raised in the article - the system of anti-systemic attitudes - is quite

oxymoronic, this task is not impossible if to have a closer look at texts that are usually ignored in the context of McLuhan's best-known works, such as "Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man". In some of the texts, however, McLuhan reveals more about the behind-the-scenes magic of his research.

It is difficult to embrace the full variety of McLuhan's ideas as to what could change the theoretical analysis. Therefore, the scientific problem in this article is the analysis of the three aspects of McLuhan's non-systematic media research - the nature of the researcher, the nature of the research, and the impact of the research outcomes on the reader.

However, it will not be limited to that. As mentioned earlier, McLuhan is not characterized by systematic communication of ideas. As a result, this type of quest usually ends up with a collection of semi-anecdotal accounts of the oddities of McLuhan's texts. In the case of this study, an attempt will be made to find a denominator in the history of philosophy for McLuhan's insights, which have nothing in common with each other, and to demonstrate that McLuhan's media theory was a project that tried to translate some of the problems that have persisted throughout the history of philosophy into the modern language of the electric age.

Theoretical framework

This article is based on a systematic historical analysis of McLuhan's texts, read from a methodological perspective on the problematization of the French sociologist and philosopher Michael Foucault. Although the term "problematization" appears in Foucault's late texts and interviews very often, its content, thanks to the author of the term itself, has remained without clear definition (Lawlor 2014: 302).

There are many features of problematization as a research methodology; two of them have been used in this article. First, problematization as a methodology is characterized by paying special attention to those thinking and lifestyle events that are seen as problems at a certain historical moment. Second, problematization, from Foucault's point of view, also raises a genealogical question of how the perceptions of certain thinking events as problems are interrelated and what the possible causes are. Therefore, the article also seeks to indicate the origins of certain McLuhan's ideas on media cognition.

In terms of material, problematization directs the research to those McLuhan's texts in which his views on media cognition were still being formed or vice versa, which reflected the application of methods of media analysis. Basically, the focus is on the periphery of McLuhan's textual legacy - his literary texts, various interviews, and smaller publications. A closer look at these texts allowed us to take a fresh look at the better-known works by McLuhan.

Results and Discussion

1. Researcher as an Amateur

In one interview, McLuhan explains his relationship with the research object by creating a broad field of metaphors rather than by defining it in terms. He says:

The better part of my work on media is actually somewhat like a safe-cracker's. I don't know what's inside; maybe it's nothing. I just sit down and start to work. I

gropes, I listen, I test, I accept and discard; I try out different sequences—until the tumblers fall and the doors spring open. (McLuhan 1967: 270)

From this statement, it can be inferred that McLuhan attempts to describe a more general exploratory relationship by the metaphor of the safe-cracker. For him, it is a way of perceiving what is more characteristic of conversation than of written literature. In conversation, verbal research is uneven and nonlinear (McLuhan et al. 2011: 23). The results obtained in such research may be true or false, but McLuhan does not verify their reliability. “You don’t like those ideas? I got others,” says one of his famous aphorisms.

McLuhan’s multi-perspective position on the relationship with the object is reminiscent of Walter Benjamin’s opposition of the two types of perception, which he described as *gesammelt* and *zerstreut* (Benjamin 2017: 31). *Gesammelt* is the establishment of connections between individual objects of reality through thinking, giving it a unified, purposeful meaning. However, the relationship of modern man with the environment is different due to the intensity of the environment - it is *zerstreut*, scattered and not conceptualizing.

Thus, McLuhan's research seems to be more characterized by Benjamin’s proposed method of diffuse perception, where the information provided by the senses is not united by any centralizing idea; they remain in the form of everyday practical insights. Such dispersion of thought is more characteristic of spoken communication, so it is not surprising that McLuhan's written texts primarily focus on the stylistics of the conversation: the main ideas are formulated in short aphorisms (McLuhan believed that short wordings are more acceptable to consumers of electrical media - the "secondary orality" era (Ong 2012: 51)); the reader himself/ herself is responsible for comprehension ("the user is the content"); thoughts are formulated in the form of a joke. McLuhan's biographer Philip Marchand explains the style, incompatible with the seriousness of science, by the fact that McLuhan used the language not as a means to formulate thought - the result of thinking, but as a tool for the examination of thought itself (Marchand 1998: 131). In one of perhaps the most radical implementations of this strategy, "The Medium is the Massage", McLuhan describes a character engaged in such a comprehensive examination as an amateur, as opposed to a specialized research professional. McLuhan points to the main advantage of an amateur over a professional: "The amateur can afford to lose" (McLuhan 1967: 282).

2. In (re)search for an effect

One way to explain McLuhan’s position of media criticism is by borrowing Pierre Hadot’s description of ancient philosophy as a practice (Ralón 2012: 199). The content McLuhan gave to this concept and a partial genealogy of it will be revealed in the article later based on McLuhan's texts written before his well-known studies on media.

The origins of McLuhan's anti-theoretical attitude are primarily attributed to the so-called practical criticism. In the 1940s, it was very popular at the University of Cambridge, where McLuhan worked and wrote his dissertation at that time. The representatives of practical criticism suggested that one should refuse to evaluate the work from a theoretical distance, and advised the critic to try to perform it (Rhodes

2009: 33). In “performance,” work becomes a perceived environment that changes the sensory and intellectual possibilities of who there is in it. The description, or documentation of this process is the goal of practical criticism (Richards 2008: 221).

McLuhan liked to emphasize the non-identity between science and himself based on theory - a set of abstract principles. "As an investigator, I have no fixed point of view, no commitment to any theory – my own or anyone else’s", said McLuhan (McLuhan 1970: 9). In this statement, attention should be drawn to the motive of uncertainty and dynamics, opposed to the theory. Theory, in McLuhan's view, allows only a certain rhythm of repetitions, but deprives the possibility of any innovation. The theoretical model is characterized by rhythm of repetition focused on maintaining stability. But stability, in McLuhan’s conception, cannot be called communication, because it is always a change (McLuhan 1969: 43-44). Communication always changes the recipient, so communication only happens when the recipient changes. Communication theories are mostly about the transfer of information from the sender to the recipient, but it is not the theory of communication, as McLuhan states it, it is the theory of information transfer. Change does not require the maintenance of stability, it needs a certain state of "leap": "no effect, no communication", as McLuhan said. Only effect reduces ignorance.

No wonder that McLuhan turned to art of language and poetry in his search for such effects. He argued that what we call poetry is indeed an act of communication when, in terms of communication technology, input is weak but sensory response is strong (McLuhan 1970: 8).

The effect changes the recipient, and the change is turned into technology, media. In a letter to Ralph Cohen, the editor of "New Literary History" (Siskin 2009: 720), McLuhan wrote that media is a mythologized form of the senses. In the letter, McLuhan mentions that James Joyce discovered that all technology came from fantasies about the human body. Joyce said the human body was the most important source of the history of technology, because at some point in the history of the human body, due to a certain impulse or crisis, some functions of the body are turned into abstract schemes and repeated in modified forms outside the body (Molinaro 1988: 332). In this letter, McLuhan also raised the idea that the object of the history of communication is the history of changes in the human body. It is a pity Cohen was not interested in these ideas, but Eric McLuhan (McLuhan 1971: 86) said that his father had composed something akin to a project of the history of communication as an effect, and he marked places which could be included in such a story in various books.

In one interview (McLuhan 1997: 66), McLuhan called his study "Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man" a toolkit for analysis and understanding. It is a text that did not arise from the theoretical modelling of media features, but from their performative performance and was intended (as a travel guide) for practical use. McLuhan said he was ready to abandon any of his previous statements at any time if it turned out that it was not appropriate for the problem emerging in a new form. At the same time, he did not think it could be said that he was the owner or author of the statements. What he did was a procedure of

exaggerating, testing an idea, or an object in extreme circumstances. McLuhan called himself a detective, as he used his senses consciously and gave some environmental objects more importance than others, just not by using the magnifying glass of theory, but in the way artists do it (McLuhan 1967: 267). In this way, it revealed the hidden environmental effects and the impact on us. The detective, according to McLuhan, is a true aesthete of the electric age (McLuhan 2015: 143).

The seven subsections of McLuhan's first chapter of "Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man" are like magnifications that show seven peculiarities of media and their effects. McLuhan seems to have compiled the book on the basis of the structure of one of the most important studies on practical criticism, "Understanding Poetry" (Brooks 1943: 341), and linked his own study to the latter. "Understanding Poetry" was one of the most influential texts that affected post-war U.S. intellectuals and presented literature as an environment in which the reader not only received a message in the form of information, but – most importantly – had to pay attention to the correlation between formal elements of text organization and their own senses. The influence of literary forms is relatively independent of their content, so it is a rather important change in the traditional concept of literature in practical criticism: the structure of a literary form (genre, etc.) is more important than the information it conveys. One of the statements most debated by the theorists of practical criticism is a traditional view of literature as a decorated truth. In practical criticism, so-called decor (rhyme, rhythm, rhetorical elements) is the feature of the literary communication environment (media) that should be considered in order to understand the impact of literature (Bennett 1977: 570). In "Understanding Poetry", attention is drawn to the phenomenon that even when the reader knows the story, he/ she reads or listens to it. Thus, the reader or the viewer is more interested in the environment (media) than in the story itself.

Discussions on literary theory at the University of Cambridge in the 1930s highlighted the view that practical criticism is a universal intellectual attitude that encompasses not only the arts but all human activities. Such is the "all-key" of criticism if we were to develop McLuhan himself as an allegory of a safe-cracker, the application of which would always have to be re-done in order to access the contents of the safe-deposit box.

3. Research as television watching

Over the past few years, researchers have begun to agree that the key question concerning McLuhan is how this scientist made everyone talk about him so much. One of the latest monographs on McLuhan's ideas by the Italian scientist Elena Lamberti offers to try to read the way something was said rather than what was said (Lamberti 2012: 52). Moreover, she hints that if McLuhan's deep writing structures are to be grasped, one may have to dismantle his creative legacy into fragments and recompose.

Interestingly, McLuhan only became concerned about the effects of his own texts on the reader after "The Mechanical Bride: Folklore of Industrial Man" was published in 1951. After accusing the publisher, he finally admitted that he had failed

to talk about an industrial man because the way to affect the audience by saying was not found (McLuhan 2011: 17).

McLuhan's search for a more efficient way of writing, as can be seen from his later letters, turned to those modernist writing techniques that sought to modify classical forms of myth to be suitable to tell an industrial man about his world. One of McLuhan's most discerning researchers, Donald Theall, thinks that McLuhan discovered the recipe for using the myth technique in the modern world by reading Joyce (Theall 2006: 172). It is about the so-called "little epic" - epyllion (ἐπύλλιον) genre - structurally described as a story in a story, or a performative interaction between two stories. As mentioned in research on McLuhan's biography (Marchand 1998: 71), in the mid 1940s, McLuhan was simply obsessed with the epyllion, the poetics of constructing multi-story interrelationships, which seemed to be the key to the mystery of all Western literature.

Speaking of epyllion, McLuhan emphasizes that the most important in this genre is a binary system of plots or situations, each of which can be both primary and secondary (McLuhan 2015: 211). The most important thing in the epyllion genre is that the secondary story acts as the one transforming the primary or - McLuhan finds it even more important - a factor providing a dimension of "spirituality" (Molinaro 1988: 221).

One might get the impression that McLuhan is simply trying to regenerate an archaic genre, forcing it to function in a new communicative situation. As can be seen from McLuhan's remarks on this genre, he was less concerned with the classic epyllion genre than with the ability to communicate with poorly defined multi-element poetics. Therefore, in explaining his choice of epyllion, McLuhan sees the possibilities it offers in parallel with Japanese haiku, traditional English Baroque heroic couplets, and ideograms. Considering all these genre derivatives, McLuhan concludes that the essence of all artistic activity generally lies in such binary or multi-element systems (Molinaro 1988: 311).

McLuhan notes that Ovid uses epyllion to incorporate the facts of technological history into the field of poetic reflection (Molinaro 1988: 281), while Dante uses epyllion in his "Divine Comedy" consistently, as it is one of the most popular Renaissance poetic forms (Molinaro 1988: 324). According to McLuhan, Edgar Allan Poe rediscovers Ovid's ancient parallel stories or action techniques and creates what McLuhan calls the "interval technique" (McLuhan and Nevitt 1972: 163), where in a detective story the emptiness between crime and its interpretation becomes central to reader engagement. But it is only in Joyce's work that McLuhan discovers such a binary-speaking manner as a total program to control the chaos of the present by means of the structures of the past.

This feature of Joyce's poetics was already noted by Thomas Stearns Eliot in his essay "Ulysses', Order, and Myth" in 1923. He raised the idea that it is Joyce who owns the discovery that myth, as a form of the past, gives meaning and order to "the inferiority and anarchy of present history" (Eliot 2001). By telling historical processes in such binary poetics, a kind of cubist construction is obtained, in which everything finds itself in the present with no perspective of the past. McLuhan

expands on this idea of history in the present by interpreting Joyce's idea that all popular culture, games, and the most banal everyday conversations are permeated by the importance of collective human history (McLuhan 1953: 102).

In general, as McLuhan points out, all human reality is full of a wide variety of divisions and interfaces, the most essential of which seemed to be the division between visual and acoustic space. However, the division immediately becomes an interface, the separated worlds are involved in parallel correlating processes, which in turn provoke a sense of community, even universality. And it does not matter at all whether two cultures, two events, or two ideas find themselves in a state of such commonality, in each case there will always be that exchange between them, sometimes even a magical transformation. And the more different the interacting elements, the greater the tension between them (McLuhan 2007: 63).

McLuhan's vision of how this multi-layered narrative poetry works in the text is worth quoting in more detail:

The first line presents the situation; the second presents the effect on the sensibilities. The discovery that you could present effects directly and that one could bypass the cause of the effect, led to many developments in the arts in the past century. In a sense, it is embodied in my phrase "the medium is the message" in the way I present the effect of the medium on the sensibilities in a way that bypasses causes, at least those causes most people locate in the content. (Molinaro 1988: 341)

After publishing "The Mechanical Bride: Folklore of Industrial Man", McLuhan, as he himself points out in his letters, chooses the sensuality of the Eastern Christian (Orthodox) Church (Molinaro 1988: 97), or the strategy of television narrative (apparently, it is an even more important parallel). Commenting on the links between television and the epyllion genre, McLuhan argues that television does not show images, it is like a source of X-rays penetrating our body. Therefore, in this case, according to McLuhan, we are more confronted with a kind of tactical experience, when the rays penetrating the screen glass reach us and connect what and how it is told (television) with an observer responding to the sensations of television screen combinations with a stream of light (Molinaro 1988: 99).

So, the epyllion genre, in McLuhan's understanding, helps the reader of the electrical age engage in a familiar and favourite practice for him/ her - the text he/ she is reading makes him/ her feel as if he/ she is watching TV. McLuhan's belief in the possibility of such sensory manipulations — reading as if watching television — is best illustrated by his unfinished project to create a special room to mimic sensory experiences from different cultures and historical epochs (Marchand 1998: 109).

4. Theory as a creative puzzle

At times, McLuhan reacted to the comments on his ideas in the same way as in the famous scene of Woody Allen's "Annie Hall" (Movieclips 2016). And once, unable to bear the accusations that he was an enemy of book culture, McLuhan replied that most of his texts were like Menippean satires in which he portrayed the everyday life of the world as a joke (Molinaro 1988: 77). So, reading his statements literally means not understanding anything.

What are Menippean satires? Mikhail Bakhtin cited 14 features of Menippean satires that he discovered in various periods of this genre (Bakhtin 1984: 98). They are comic or carnival elements in the story, freedom of transformation of ideas and stories, non-observance of media and genre boundaries, emphasizing formal features of genre or media more than content, the priority of current issues over the past.

At first glance, all these features of Menippean satires can be found in McLuhan's texts. However, the biggest intrigue is related to the so-called quaternary system of media laws, which the McLuhans - father and son - present in "Laws of Media: The New Science". The book begins by stating that more than 12 years of consistent research have shown that it is impossible to find the fifth law common to all media (McLuhan 2007: 42). Such a statement could show arrogance, but one could also see a satirical blink to the reader prompting how the statements made should be accepted. How is it actually?

Having revealed the traces of the so-called media laws in McLuhan's previous texts, it is clear that three of these laws - extend, reverse, obsolesce - have already been mentioned in "Understanding Media", one of them in the book title itself. In another book, "From Cliche to Archetype", another law emerges - retrieve. Based on William B. Yeats' poem "The Circus Animals' Desertion", McLuhan formulates the principle of creativity capable of updating and adapting the technologies and ideas of previous cultural epochs to new functions (McLuhan 2015: 87). However, these new concepts of the media system do not dispel the overall impression - all seven books between "Understanding Media" and "The Laws of Media" say essentially nothing new that would not have been published in the first three McLuhan's books - "The Mechanical Bride", "The Gutenberg Galaxy", and "Understanding Media". Clearly, instead of surprising the reader with new ideas and erudition, McLuhan begins to repeat essentially the same things. The lack of ideas is hardly to blame here, most likely it happened for another reason. What was that reason?

Researchers of oral culture have found that repetition, turning into a stereotype or cliché, is not just a tool to help remember better. Repetition also helps refine the idea. Therefore, one should not speak of repetition only as an aid, as it is directly related to intellectual activity (Lord 2019: 75). All the more so because repetition does not have the possibility to be always the same - let the basic formula remain, but the context always changes, as well as the unique personal or social conditions.

At the very beginning of "Understanding Media", McLuhan warns the readers that media content often overshadows the nature of media (McLuhan 2015: 231). It can therefore be said that, in his later texts, McLuhan embodies his main thesis, "the medium is the message." The content of the books does not help readers to learn anything more about the world, but it helps to find new forms of awareness and intellectual vigilance adequate to ever new social or technological changes. What can be called distillation, or the purification of essential statements about the media, takes place before the reader's eyes, the thinking of the media becoming a very clear system of concepts - the four laws of the media.

Of course, the reader should notice that this distillation process undermines some of McLuhan's previous ideas, which seemed very important. Let us say that one

idea - a continuation of the senses as sensory amputation - becomes less and less noticeable after "Understanding Media", as if repeating the statements about the impact of the media on a person makes its incapacity increasingly clear. Almost all media-related insights undergo one or another transformation. There is, however, one element that remains in all subsequent McLuhan's trials of his own theses: satire. Satire was first understood by McLuhan as a reader training for reflection (McLuhan 2007: 223). Satire, understood in this very broad sense, is characteristic of almost all McLuhan's texts without exception.

All of McLuhan's books written after "Understanding Media" have the same attitude - not to explain, but to leave the reader to find answers by himself / herself in a story that emerges in search of hidden connections between the very heterogeneous elements presented. The reader's job is to comprehend the maze of contextual dynamics, and the way to do it is no longer McLuhan's concern (Turner 1966: 16).

However, McLuhan provides some general principles of navigation in this maze. In one letter, he mentions a book, in which he has succeeded in proving that the connections between all human artefacts, both material and mental, are of a linguistic nature (Molinaro 1988: 117). Reflections of these ideas also appear in "The Laws of Media": "utterings are outerings", as Eric McLuhan argues, i.e., sayings are sequels, so the media is not like words, they are words, so the verbal structure of the media is the biggest challenge for the researcher (McLuhan 2007: 241).

When it comes to media laws, McLuhan's rhetorical system becomes the key to revealing the fundamental quartet of media principles. Since the time of his dissertation on Thomas Nashe, McLuhan loved a five-part structure based on five systematic parts of rhetoric: invention, arrangement, style, memory, and delivery. According to biographers, McLuhan was obsessed with the idea of finding structural equivalents of the five parts everywhere (Gordon 2002: 257). Only parts of this rhetoric in McLuhan's conception are one-time, acting simultaneously, and the script and especially the press dismantles them, arranging them as if in a sequence and thus destroying the possibility of experiencing the analyzed objects as a whole.

However, an inconsistency that really bothers the reader arises - the four media laws constantly appear in the book against the background of five-part constructions. The most striking of these are the five parts of the book "Laws of Media".

In the first four parts of the book, four media laws are formulated and demonstrated. Narration style is scientific, the relationship between cause and effect is constantly emphasized. However, the fifth part, "Media Poetics", sets out to analyze the media tetrad itself as a kind of a rhetorical figure. McLuhan discusses the complex of media laws with the concepts of metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, and irony, commenting on them as mathematically accurate various interactions between figure and background. Metaphor for him is two pairs of figure-background models; in the case of metonymy there is no figure, there is only the interaction of two backgrounds. The intrigue does not arise from trying to delve into these analytical cascades of media laws, finding a reference to the next one at each stage, but unexpectedly discovering that in a paranoid search for all possible figure-background pair combinations, one is missing - two figures and one background.

The reader of McLuhan's texts has to be very careful. Solving this task - why one of the possible combinations was missed - should help to overcome the constant self-deception that everything is clear, a provision that, according to McLuhan, each of us practices (Molinaro 1988: 81).

How can we interpret that missing combination of two figures and one background? In the context of the same background, the presence of two different figures is inevitably comical, carnival, which is one of the hallmarks of the Menippean satire. Many situations in today's mass comedy industry are based on this very principle, for example, showing the adventures of a city dweller when he/ she finds himself/ herself in a village or otherwise modelling a situation so that the participation of one figure in the same background would inevitably be funny.

If we try to draw conclusions not only from what McLuhan wrote, but also from what he demonstratively missed to write, satire seems to be the fifth media law the unsuccessful search for which is theatrically mentioned at the beginning of "Laws of Media". The tetrad of media laws itself and its argumentation can be understood as the Menippean satire. The latter genre is sometimes described as integrating the performativity of an amateur and the seriousness of a scientist, as a kind of scientific literature, in which one finds jokes that can be understood only in the intellectual community sharing the same knowledge and interests (Blanchard 1995: 85). The fifth law of the media - satire - seems to be a joke that can be detected and understood in the tetrad of media laws only by the participants of a closed academic group.

5. Retrieve of St. Thomas Aquinas

At this point, the study could be concluded by saying that McLuhan presented a set of unrelated propositions instead of a theoretical framework. And with that, his rebellion against the theory that limits thinking is complete. This is usually the case, but in this instance we will nevertheless try to overcome McLuhan's reputation as a pop thinker who is unable to create a clear system of concepts and relate it to the tradition of the history of ideas (Stewart, 2015).

A careful reading of McLuhan's *magnum opus* "Understanding Media" reveals an unusual thought for the famous media theorist, which demonstrates a concern - how could one find something that would unify the vastly diverse information transmitted by the senses into summarizing states of consciousness? (McLuhan 2015: 60). This question can also be understood as a concern for the fate of one's own theory. It seems that what was important for McLuhan, after dismantling the methodologically unified process of scientific cognition, was nevertheless to eventually find something that would provide a basis for uniting very diverse cognitive information from the same ideological perspective.

In this place, McLuhan unexpectedly remembers "common sense", which, according to the media theorist, has served for centuries as a way to unify various experiences into a whole. McLuhan continues to ask one of the most important questions in his studies of the media, which is unfortunately rarely researched: which of the senses could take on the role that "common sense" has long played in Western culture?

Having mentioned "common sense" and the senses in one place, McLuhan tricks the reader, because in his book "The Gutenberg Galaxy" published a little earlier than "Understanding media", he mentions one of the most important medieval philosophers, St. Thomas Aquinas (McLuhan 1962: 23), who answered the question of the principle that unites the senses. Bearing in mind that McLuhan liked to call himself a neo-Thomist (Heynickx & Symons 2018: 65), it is worth taking a closer look at the ideas of this scholastic philosopher about the human senses and in what way they interrelate into a coherent worldview.

St. Thomas Aquinas writes his comments about the unifying factors of the human senses while commenting on the question discussed in Aristotle's work "De Anime" about the differences of the senses and about the need to answer the question of how the human consciousness is able to harmonize this completely different information with each other (Pasnau 1999: 602).

In response to this task formulated by Aristotle, St. Thomas Aquinas says in his commentary that there should be an equivalent in the senses of what is "sensus communis". Without clearly developing his argument, he asserts that touch harmonizes the variety of senses (Pasnau 1999: 602).

It is not our task to explain how St. Thomas Aquinas' argument is justified, especially since in later times, while returning to the same question of the unity of information provided by the senses, St. Thomas Aquinas' proposal was largely unchallenged. For example, in the 17th and 18th centuries, when solving the so-called Molineaux problem, St. Thomas Aquinas' argument that the sense of touch makes it possible to combine the information provided by different senses into a unified view of the same world is still in use. First stated in the philosopher John Lock's essay "An Essay Concerning Human Understanding" (Fuller, Stecker & Wright 2000: 44), the so-called Molineaux problem is about a blind man who learned to distinguish a cube from a sphere by touch. And when he magically sees, he can distinguish between those two geometric figures even without being able to touch them. Usually, the explanation of such a communicative paradox was related to the fact that touch is a kind of meta-sense, and the others are only derivatives. In other words, the argument formulated by St. Thomas Aquinas was used.

In his media theory, McLuhan said that in modern times the function of the senses is being taken over by technologies. Therefore, although he considered himself a neo-Thomist, he could not simply adapt the argument of St. Thomas Aquinas. As our research has shown, McLuhan spoke out at every opportunity against cognitive theorizing that limits information to a single channel, thereby fundamentally distorting the human way of knowing the world. However, being a philosophizing "safe-cracker" you need something to unify all the information you receive, like the "sensus communis" or its sensory equivalent, touch. And if the senses are replaced by technology, which technology takes over this function of unifying touch?

McLuhan's view of TV as a tactile medium is well known. From the point of view of a media philosopher, TV is a myopic medium that destroys distance, and therefore we do not watch TV, but experience it as if touching, engaging in the flow of information with all our senses (McLuhan 2015: 314).

For McLuhan, TV technology seems to replace the sense of touch, because technology is more important than senses in the relationship of the person of the electric age with the environment. For this reason, McLuhan believed that TV is the same technological basis for unifying very different information of the reality, which in its function is completely analogous to the sense of touch, to which Thomas Aquinas attributed the power of unification. That is why McLuhan wanted his reader to feel with the book as if he/ she were sitting in front of the television screen, because this way of perceiving information, as it seemed to him, was much more comprehensive than reading.

Therefore, it can be said that McLuhan is a neo-Thomist not because he treats the sense of touch as a unifying factor, but because he, as it were, translates Thomas Aquinas' idea about the relationship between the sense of touch and "common sense" into a new type of formation – for him, TV technology is the same unifying factor of communication as "common sense".

Conclusion

McLuhan is generally perceived as a creator of media theory, but closer analysis shows that he was more concerned with creating a media cognition system that would allow the researcher to be inconsistent, free from stable conceptual models, and to constantly change his/ her relationship with the subject. According to McLuhan, theory only limits cognition, so understanding the media requires a system of practices that can, on the one hand, assess the nature of the transmission of information and, on the other hand, observe the changes that the information has caused to the recipient. While analysing the three aspects of McLuhan's anti-theoretical theory - the researcher, the nature of the research, and its outcome, a system of metaphors was discovered that 1) describes the researcher as an amateur who is no longer required to adhere to conceptual models; 2) defines the research itself as a cycle with no clear end, in which the outcome is replaced by an endless process of media observation; 3) compares the outcome of the research itself with watching television and the experiences typical of such an activity. Apparently, McLuhan, after having dismantling media theory into a set of poorly interconnected experiments, adventures, and performances, had to stop and feel satisfied with the outcome, but he set out to find the denominator uniting all imaginable media research practices. A study of the hints and riddles left in McLuhan's late texts seems to provide ample grounds for claiming that the common denominator of all of McLuhan's media anti-theory is TV technology, which in the age of new media replaces the sense of touch, the equivalent of "common sense" recognized in the history of philosophy since Thomas Aquinas.

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